

An isolated lithic artefact (NVL200) from Bever-Akrenbos (Belgium)

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Fig. 1

1. Description and illustration

Length:	46,5 mm
Width:	36 mm
Thickness:	12,5 mm
Weight:	22,24 g

The artefact (ID: NVL200) is a scraper manufactured from unspecified black flint with a vitreous texture. Retouch is present on both the dorsal and ventral surfaces, extending (ergonomic or hafting related?) along the right lateral edge and covering both proximal and distal portions of the artefact. No macroscopic use-wear or residu traces were recorded.

Overall, NLV200 can be interpreted as a formal flint scraper with extensive edge modification, likely designed for repeated use and potentially hafted, although direct functional evidence (use-wear or residue) is absent.

Fig. 2

2. Chronological/cultural attribution

The scraper can only be broadly dated to the Mesolithic-Neolithic period.
